

THE ISSUE OF JUSTICE IN THE WORK “MAKTUBOTI AMIR HAYDAR”

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12218851>

Annotation: In this article, the letters of Amir Haidar, one of the rulers of Bukhara, were analyzed on various issues and their significance in terms of the period in which they were written. Along with this, during the reign of Amir Haydar, his decisions on justice issues were studied.

Key words: justice, society, state, religion, zakat, education, development, secularity, spirituality, citizen, manuscript, tyranny.

It is known that many just kings, sultans and emirs have passed in the history of our statehood. Historians have left a lot of information in their works about the work they did to develop the state and society, manage the people with justice, the measures and methods they used. These works have great ideological, scientific-historical, artistic value and importance. However, the edicts and decrees issued by the rulers, letters and the instructions and tasks described in them show the approach of that ruler to various issues and his personal attitude to their solution. From this point of view, it becomes clear that these documents are also of special importance.

“Maktuboti Amir Haydar” is a collection of letters sent by Amir Haidar to devanbegi, mehtar and other officials who were high officials of the state during his reign. In this collection of letters, there are letters related to many areas of state and community life, and they are rich in terms of subject and content.

This work has not been translated or published, and a manuscript copy is stored in the fund of the Institute of Oriental Studies named after Abu Rayhan Beruni under the number AR-5412. We used this summary in the article.

Amir Haydar (1775-1826) was the son of Amir Shahmurad, and he is mentioned in the second place after his father in terms of justice and kindness among the rulers of Mangite. He ruled in 1800-1826 and experienced great hardships for the welfare of the country. Fighting against various conspiracies that started after the death of his father, his life was spent mainly in battles. At the same time, he made tireless efforts to prevent tyranny in the country and to please the citizens. In one letter, he sent a letter to Muhammad Hakimbi, who was working as a mehtar, in which he pointed out that there were cases of

injustice against the people in the collection of zakat and that it should be quickly eliminated and the way to eliminate it. The letter was as follows:

“Respected, to the Khan’s confidant Muhammad Hakimbi Mehtar.

Let them know that they should buy 250 sheep and send them to the highest dargah as soon as this letter of grace arrives. Also send the province’s bill through a trusted person.

One of your people oppressed the people a lot in the matter of zakat.

When we were in the government of Kashi, we used to make compromises with the khangorats in the matter of zakat. Now we are in Bukhara. Be kind to the neighbors, don’t oppress them. Look at the Ersori community, they don’t have a single fortress from the tyranny.

The other side is that in the Day of Resurrection, Allah Almighty will ask us and you, “Why did you do wrong?” We will say: “We thought that Muhammad Hakimbi was a good and just person and ordered him to do this service”, and you will be responsible.

In these times, everyone has become unable to control their ego. Don’t believe that person’s words and make excuses. Send someone else to re-study the issue of zakat. Let him research it. If there is a place of oppression, let him see the action to eliminate it. If he has not been wronged, let him return.

Great Amirul Umaro Muhammad Sayyidbiy Ataliq came here from Baliun. They submitted this by writing a letter. I sent someone to that person.

Oppression does not correspond to tradition or Sharia. Religion is also necessary. A person will have to pay for them on the Day of Resurrection. By the time Mubarak reached our ears, Naqib had killed Esh Qarovulbegi. Is this true or not? Your sender will tell you the rest. Assalomu alaykum. 1216 (1801)”[1].

From the content of the above letter, we can see Amir Haidar’s passion for leading the society with justice and tireless efforts. We can also see the subtle and instructive aspects of his admonition to his subordinates as a spiritually perfect person, and his analysis of the issue from a religious and secular point of view.

We will see another such letter. From the contents of this letter, we can see that Amir Haydar was well aware of the situation and conditions in every madrasa in Bukhara and he solved any problems in any madrasa. The letter also means that Amir Haydar is a lover of the field of education and people of science. We quote the letter below:

Respected leader, holding a prestigious position, a trustworthy individual of the state, Muhammad Hakim Devonbyegi.

Let them know with gratitude that, enriched with honorable rewards, we allocate a stipend of one thousand from the zakat fund of our high madrasa to the students of the Qur'an and seeker of knowledge every month. We had instructed you to also give them a small amount. However, our allocated money was less. Because of this, they are given less money, or maybe it has not been given at all for a month or two.

We made a rule. According to this, when the money for zakat ran out, we used to borrow money from the rich and give it to the students of the Qur'an and the students of the higher madrasa. When it was time for zakat, we used to settle their zakat debts. Now you borrow money from the rich and give it to the students of the Koran and the students of the higher madrasa. Inshallah, we will settle accounts with them at the time of zakat. May the mission reach the snow on the Ark and its listeners. Assalomu alaykum[2].

All the letters collected in "Maktuboti Amir Haydar" contain simple to complex issues related to the life of the state and society. In the future, if it is translated and published with the necessary comments, the minds of the general public and young people will be enriched with new information about the state system of our ancestors and their actions in the way of building a just society.

References:

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